

Evasion Expressions Used by EFL University Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 23, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Students, Grammatical, EFL Iraqi, Evasion Expressions</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5602088</p>	<p><i>The current study deals with "evasion expressions". These expressions denotes methods for rejecting from being obvious, with holding pieces of significant and honest information. The problem of the present study is that EFL Iraqi learners face some difficulties to answer certain questions. It is aimed at re-visiting the concept of "evasion expressions", their types, functions, strategies as well as measuring EFL Iraqi learners' "evasion expressions" through their answering the concerned questions. To perform such aims, the following procedures can be adopted:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Describing the notion of "evasion expressions". 2. Surveying the major types of "evasion expressions", functions and the strategies of evasion. 3. Following Galasinski (1996)' model. <p><i>3. The basic points will be outlined.</i></p> <p><i>It is hypothesized that students use both overt and covert evasion to escape from some questions. As far as the data analysis is concerned, it is limited to (30) of the EFL Iraqi learners who are fourth-year students/ Department of English/College of Education for Humanities/ University of Babylon for the academic year 2020-2021. The finding is that students actually use certain strategies of evasion to escape from some questions.</i></p>

Introduction

The objective of the present paper is to recognize the employment of evasion in students' answers as well as identify the basic types of evasion that are frequently used. Additionally, it will be pointed out the functions and strategies of evasion in their responses. Such "evasion expressions" indicate the performance of avoiding something that one does not want doing or dealing with.

"Evasion expressions" can be both covert evasion and overt evasion. These expressions will be investigated via measuring answers for certain questions of EFL Iraqi learners. That is to say, it will be analyzed the papers that are proposed by the concerned learners to show whether they use such expressions or not.

The present study is categorized into two sections. The first section discusses the concept of evasion, its types, functions, strategies as well as illustrates other issues that are related. The second section uncovers the methodology of the study that is, in its turn, explicated the procedures to measure the level of students' responses of the concerned expressions.

1.1 Literature Review

In the present section, it will be focused on concept of evasion, its types, functions and strategies. Furthermore, it will also be discussed the reasons behind students' use of evasion.

1.2.1 The Concept of Evasion

Bradak (1983: 42) states that evasion messages are approaches for disagreeing from being obvious, with holding pieces of honest and important information. On this ground, Dillon (1990:55) suggests what evasion is, that no response reactions, those deal coherently to the procession of addressees yet not to the question sentences. The notion 'evasion's accurate historical antecedent is agreed being the Latin action word "evader", which denotes "to escape".

Ng and Bradak (1993: 117) mention that evasive replies are not related to the question. Hesitant messages are those predicted as not essential. Such definition presents the notion of aim in the portrayals of evasion. Firstly, it is significant to make qualifications between unimportance all in all and in crucial that may tally evasion. Questioners who do not interpret that the persons are offering superfluous comments (e.g., subsequent to ignoring to understand an inquiry) cannot clearly, be held in charge of evasion. An individual cannot avert and does not understand it. Secondly, not all suggested insignificance regards evasion. Unimportant comments made to make a questioner disrupt or to chuckle the discussion is not simply, sly, on the basis that there is nothing to avoid.

For Obeng (1997:58), any matter in students' responses utilize a verbal indirectness as one of the crucial sides. He (ibid) identifies how students want to utilize techniques like vagueness, indirectness or evasion, and

obliqueness in their interaction, due to "the rather trickery and /or risky nature of politics itself, and especially to the power of the spoken word". That is, the appearance of evasion in students' communication is decided by the way by which the learners use to response the questions beside the reaction of the addressers towards the addressee, (Obeng, 2002:210).

Consequently, Galasinski (2000:40) maintains that if the speakers try not to give direct answers or challenges the questions and to escape from the right answers, in this case the responses can be evasive. Evasive expressions are those which intended being semantically insignificant. In the same vein, Mckenzie(2005:44) emphasizes that "what is of the same amount of significance to what is stated, is the thing that gets left inferred". To sum up, evasion indicates the demonstration of physically obtaining away from something, it is additionally denotes that something one should do or unpleasant circumstances through maneuvering in responses to the hard questions. Evasion exists when the information an individual receives from the speakers ignore to meet his/her desire. Regardless of whether expressions are evasive or hesitant, it relies on the data gave by the speakers. Evasion is a feature of listener translation, and such, is a perlocutionary effect. The answer "*I think you'd better ask your mother to the question Can I go out tonight?*" is potentially evasive, relying on the father's function in such matters, (ibid:59).

1.2.2 Types of Evasion

According to Galasinski (1996:19), evasion can be classified into two basic types that are covert evasion and overt evasion.

1.2.2.1 Covert Evasion

In this type, the speaker appears to liken with the "tricky or deceptive" type. Based on covert evasion, the speakers expressly flag that they will offer responses to an inquiry and in this way that they are "willing to participate". Then it involves that the speakers do not give an important / satisfactory answer in secret ways", (Galasinski, 1996:19-21).

He (ibid) adds that three types of covert evasion can be distinguished that are:

- a- The basic type of "covert evasion" is changing the printed settings of the question, which involves the speaker/answers' reference to the center. The speakers have few choices in this typology, the speakers may talk about the issue being pointed out making statements which are not justified by the inquiry's substance. The speakers can likewise "reformulate the interest of the question".
- b- The second type of covert evasion involves the speakers' changing the focal points of the inquiry. It denotes that the central contention, which is changed, is explained what in the printed setting requesting by the inquiry.
- c- The last kind of covert evasion alludes changing both the printed setting of the question and the concentration. Similarly, there are numbers of approaches which the speakers can embrace. The speakers can give expressions that incorporate propositions that are not lucidly identified with the inquiry. Those speakers may address recommendations assumed by the questions, (ibid:63).

1.2.2.2 Overt Evasion

With reference to overt evasion, it is simple to identify, in the light that individuals may not be agreeable via straight ward oral refusals. In any case, in demonstration of overt evasion, the speakers endeavor to conceal that the individuals in question do not offer helpful responses to the inquiry, or the speakers manipulate the emphasis or the content of the question, while actually it does not. Therefore, overt evasion is a characteristic that is unique that causes worry in learner's talk. Additionally, three kinds of overt evasion can be distinguished that are:

- a- To state openly.
- b- To imply.
- c- To present oneself as the one who should not be asked the question, (ibid:61).

1.2.3 Strategies of Realizing Evasion

Partington (2003:235) describes evasion as the terminal point at the straight aberrance/forwards continuum of the speakers' decision whereas addressing the questions. He (ibid) states that capturing the link between the level of hesitance procedures and the explicitness of the suitable response adopted by the speakers. It is worth mentioning that strategies of realizing evasion can be classified into six ones that are illustrated as follows:

1.2.3.1 Refusal to Answer

a- On record refusal to reply without justifications, this indicates the intentional silence of the addressee when he/she opposed by the addresser and by such answer (silence) there is some sort of reference to overt evasion, (Clayman, 2001:70).

b- On record refusal to reply with justification, learner refuses responding either he/she cannot reply or he/she does not desire to reply.

1.2.3.2 Claiming Incompetence to Answer

a- Absence of knowledge (claim of ignorance).
Absence of competence.
the charge of scope.
another person.

b-
c-Outside
d- Pointing the question to

1.2.3.3 Challenging the Question, Questioner, Source

a- Challenging the premises of the questions. The premises mean to accept the information as it is to outline such truth.
b- Challenging the authority of the enquires /questions which mean to think in various ways to give ambiguity answer to the questioners.
c- Challenging presuppositions of the questions. This indicate case in which the evaders try to present incomplete and unclear reply to presuppose the questions.
d- Challenging the facts involved in the questions. To evade on facts are mentioned in the questions.
e- Challenging the questioners.

1.2.3.4 Evasion by Humour

Humor is already utilized in the wish of averting direct answers or escaping from tough spots. For instance, in an interview with Mr.Lackhart talking about the president:

"Q:[...] but the President is a larger-than- life figure and he's somebody who gets attention every time he opens his mouth.
Mr.Lochart: Well, we're going to put him on a diet.(Laughter) He is going to be smaller, thinner ,less noticeable", (Levinson,1992:245).

In this example, the evasiveness is proved here where the question is embarrassing for the interviewee to explicate, because thathe moves to utilize the style of humor and mocking for the purpose of leaving the required answer and not to present right and direct answer.

1.2.3.5 Evasion by Claiming

The answer has already been replied, students do not agree to respond on the grounds that or widely covered that ground. They has already answered certain questions. Moral evasion can be described as a demonstration that bamboozles by explaining genuine explanations that are prompts or insignificant a false ending. For instance, "*a man realizes that another man in a room in the building in light of the fact that he heard him*", yet in answer to an inquiry utters, "*I have not seen him*", there by erroneously inferring that he does not know.

In this regard, Bull(2003:114) mentions twelve tactics that students use to evade certain questions:

- 1- To pay no attention to the addresser's question. That is, the learners disregard the interaction's questions and donot attempt to present answers.
- 2- To admit the addresser's question without providing any answer.
- 3- To ask the question of the addresser.
- 4- To present some ideas, explaining themselves, or suggest another topics. Students often tend to create thoughts and ideas through a variety of methods like: creating certain attacks, forming certain matters, appealing to nationalism, investigating particular matters, justifying themselves as well as talking about their own side.
- 4- To apologize. In this regard, Sudzczyńska (1999:1056) outlines a general approach of the apology as below:
 - 1-Illocutionary force indicating devices involving:
 - a- Expression of regrets.
 - c- Requesting forgiveness.
 - 2- Explanation any external mitigating conditions, 'objective' reason for violation'.
 - 3- Talking on responsibility involving
 - a- Express self –blame.
 - b- Absence of intent.
 - c- Expressions of self-deficiency.
 - d- Expressions of embarrassment.
 - e- Self-dispraises.
 - f- Justify hearers.
 - g- Refusal to acknowledge guilt.
- 5- Regard for the hearers.
- 6- Offer of repairs.
- 7- Promise of forbearances.
- 6- To repeat answers that he/she has already given to past questions. It is already learners refuse to answer on the questions that are already covered.
- 8- To offer incomplete answers. Different constructions of incomplete answers in interaction such as: initiating to response the addresser's question without ending it, presenting "half answers" and providing replies that are "fractional".

9- Attack the addresser. Students tend to attack those who disagree them. This denotes that not all questions present to the addressee is simple or need a natural response, so in this condition student attempts to avert the answer via attacking the addresser.

9-To state that students always provide a response. To tell or suggest that the students have already given responses to the addresser's questions.

10-Literalism or peculiarity; Bull (1991:119) affirms that "The literal aspect of question which was not intended to be taken literally is answered".

11-To criticize the addresser's question, students do so because of the following causes:

- a- The questions fail to deal with the important issues.
- b- The questions are speculative or hypothetical.
- c- The question is depended on a fail premise.
- d- The question is actually complete.
- e-The question involves misquotations.
- f- The question involves quotations taken out of context,
- g- The question is unpleasant.
- h- The question is relied on false alternatives.

12- To refuse responses to the addresser's question. Five ways can be distinguished:

- a-"refusal on grounds of inability".
- b- "unwillingness to answer".
- c-"deferred response".
- d-"It is not possible to answer the question for the time being".
- e. "pleads ignorance".

Lastly, when students do not want to be in embarrassing positions, they tend to utilize the evasion strategies that begin from postponing the answers of such questions or evading responses at all. Such strategies are concerned with the techniques of cover-up that is usually utilized as an obvious strategy, for instance, in political negotiations through it the addresser and addressee begin by concealing, (Weigand,2010:21).

1.2.4 Functions of Evasion

Clayman (1993: 39) recognizes functions and rephrase by the students when they answer any question in interaction. He (ibid) adds that two functions of this manner: (i) to make the hard questions easy ones , and (ii) to avert from the subject. Averting from questions can seem under certain conditions like:

1. Outlining the subject or changing to another topic,
2. Answering piece of question which denotes to answer the first portion of the question and avert from the second one (in questions involve two portions) by any way of evasion techniques.
3. The students choose one of two options either agreement or not.

1.2.5 Employment of Evasion

Evasion should be represented as the students' attempt to control the progressions of conversation. Refusing to address questions, or in any events, nothing it straight forwardly without full duties by the students, challenge the inquiry's entitlements to pose it. Be that as it can, the students can likewise do it by an undercover infringement of the Gricean sayings significance. For such situation, the addressee is predicted to acknowledge significance of immaterial answers without monitoring it. Moreover, the students are controlling the focal point of the questions, answers questions unique in relation to the one asked, ensuring thereby that the individual has control how the trade creates. In such away, evasion plays out its controlling functions, (Galasinski,2000:70).

That is to say, evasion is a technique that utilized by students to escape from presenting important and honest information. Students tend to utilize evasion when they feel that there is no way replying verbally to the questions lead to face threatening act. The most plain kinds of not addressing questions are by all accounts verbalized refusal to inquiries, which are particularly solid break which is for most part associated by supporting why answers are not replied, (Clayman,2001:404).

2.1 Methodology

The current section deals with the practical procedures which are explained the steps to measure the level of students' responses of the following questions:

1. What is the lesson plan to teach composition for 4th secondary school?
 2. What are the general guidelines that should be taken into consideration during students teaching?
 3. What are the main procedures should be followed by the teacher in any communicative lesson?
- Nevertheless, Galasinski (1996)'s model will be adopted in this study.

2.2 Description Test

The test is basically relied on the production one. The EFL Iraqi learners are needed to answer the concerned questions in relation to the academic strategies.

2.3 The Population

The EFL Iraqi learners subjected the test in the current study are fourth-year students/Department of English/College of Education for Humanities/ University of Babylon. The sample is about (30) learners who belong to the academic year 2020-2021. They are in the same age and they are also non-native speakers. The concerned sample is elected because they actually regard master responding the concerned questions due to their spending four years to learn English language.

2.4 Instrument

A quantitative method is employed in the current study. Williams (2011: 14) mentions that this method means analyzing and measuring variables to reach certain results. A quantitative method involves utilizing and investigating numeral data via utilizing certain statistical procedures to reach certain answers to the concerned test.

2.5 Validity and Reliability

For the purpose of making a study instrument more consistent and suitable designed, it is useful to achieve the two indispensable preconditions of "reliability and validity". Regarding validity of a test, Heaton (1974: 78) mentions that it is the extent by which it measures what it is assumed measuring and nothing else. A test should be as valid as their teachers make them. The test should aim to supply true measures of the specific skill which it is intended measuring. As far as reliability is concerned, it ought to do with stability of marks for the same students. As their scores are fixed, the test will be reliable. But if they tend to fluctuate with no obvious reasons, it will be not reliable, (Harmer, 2001: 90).

3.6 Final Administration

The final version of the test was carried out on April 2021 on (30) students that are elected randomly from the 4th year students/ Department of English/College of Education for Humanities/ University of Babylon. The EFL Iraqi learners took solely (45) minutes to write their responses. Additionally, they have been inform to write down their names. However, certain answers of students are supplied in the appendix.

3.7 Analysis of Data and Discussion

After subjecting students to the test, it will be gotten the following results:

Table (1) Frequencies of Evasion Types

Types of Evasion	Frequency	Percentage
Covert Change the Form of the Question	8	17%
Covert Change the Content of the Question	9	19%
Covert Change Both	11	23%
Overt Imply	5	11%
Overt State Openly	7	15%
Total	40	100%

Table (2) Frequencies of Evasion Functions

Functions of Evasion	Frequency	Percentage
Escape from Question	37	48%
Preserving Face	7	10%
Avoiding blame	3	22%
Reducing Negative Reaction	8	11%
Talking about Special Issues	27	37%
Keeping away from Problems	3	22%
Total	73	100%

From the preceding tables, it has been observed that the number of the evasion type of covert change both, in table (1), are (11) which rates (23%). This percentage is regarded as the highest one among other types while overt imply type scores the lowest with percentages of (11%). Concerning table (2), the number of the escape from questionnaire (37) which rates (48%). This percentage is higher than the number of both avoiding blame and keeping away from problems which are (3) that rates (22%).

3.8 Results

It has been observed that EFL Iraqi students use two types of evasion: covert evasion and overt evasion. Thus, the hypothesis, that is stated earlier, is verified. Their results reflect that they actually try to escape from the concerned questions since they have no enough information to answer accurately. So, the dominant function use is that of escaping from question. Such result may belong to many reasons. One of these reasons is that EFL Iraqi students do not study well. Another reason is that some instructors follow traditional approaches through teaching. It is suggested that learners should be more careful towards their curriculums. Besides, instructors should also follow modern methods in order to develop the scientific level of school Iraqi students as well as focusing good references.

Conclusion

The following points are concluded:

1. What evasion is, that no response reactions, those deal coherently to the procession of addressees yet not to the question sentences. The notion 'evasion's accurate historical antecedent is agreed being the Latin action word "evader", which denotes "to escape".
2. If the speakers try not to give direct answers or challenges the questions and to escape from the right answers, in this case the responses can be evasive.
3. Two basic types that are covert evasion and overt evasion. Based on covert evasion, the speakers expressly flag that they will offer responses to an inquiry and in this way that they are "willing to participate". With reference to overt evasion, it is simple to identify, in the light that individuals may not be agreeable via straight ward oral refusals.
4. Strategies of realizing evasion can be refusal to answer, claiming incompetence to answer, challenging the question, questioner, source, evasion by humour and evasion by claiming.
5. Two functions of evasion can be distinguished that are: (i) to make the hard questions easy ones, and (ii) to avert from the subject.
6. It has been observed that EFL Iraqi students use two types of evasion: covert evasion and overt evasion. Thus, the hypothesis, that is stated earlier, is verified. Their results reflect that they actually try to escape from the concerned questions since they have no enough information to answer accurately. So, the dominant function use is that of escaping from question.

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